

THE REPORT OF COOPERATION BETWEEN SCHOOL AND FAMILY

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to provide a detailed analysis of parent-teacher-student communication relationships in school, as well as their importance during the educational process. The parent and the teacher are two partners that have the same goal in child education, having a mutual purpose. As such, they should cooperate, exchange information, discuss, and debate with each other. Both parties contribute to the development, growth, and advancement of the child. The parent the child's first teacher with a lifelong experience gained over the years; while the teacher is a professional educator who possesses a special preparation, training, and experience. He is a well-trained expert, trained on theoretical and practical scientific basis. They both know the child very well; first the parent and later the teacher also. Their knowledge must complement each other. They cannot be formal, general, and unified. Every child has his own individuality in development, formation, education, his psychological traits, his personality and dignity, and his social problems, and thus every child is a specific case. All children should be respected regardless of their gender, race, religion, and their needs. Integration into a new society requires maximum commitment of the whole society. Preparing the new generation to cope with the challenges of the unknown requires a reformed and quality education. An advanced and qualitative European-wide education is the main pillar of the empowerment of our new state. In this context, our society has seen the need for radical reforms in education at all levels. Reforms in education are focused on the whole society for the purpose of its progress.

Keywords: partnership, school, family, parent, student, teacher

1. Reports of cooperation between school and family

Parents want their children to grow up, to be trained and educated in a worthwhile circle of family, environment, and society. From the time when a parent registers a child at school, parent-student and parent-child communication routes must be always open.

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Therefore, open communication channels between school and family are set up at the beginning of the school year.

The opportunities to meet, talk about the program, the children and the wishes of the parents are an integral part of the plan for the whole school year. Teacher benefits more because it begins to get closer to the students' family and community life, as well as the traditions, rituals and activities or needs and concerns of particular families, and may be able to meet those needs.

The teacher must convey to parents that they want to work with them in order to transform the schools into a place where the child wants to go willingly. All children benefit from positive and friendly relationships between family and school. This is a step that ensures the child a proper support, especially when he needs the most.

It should also be acknowledged, respected, and supported the importance of the parent as the first teacher and expert in recognizing the child in particular. Both in pre-school and in primary school, parents are considered as partners of the teachers in the child education process. Parents represent the first models of problem solving; cooperation; and exchange of information, or any other thing, mutually.

Purposely parents teach their children on how to be integrated into a community and become of an integral part of a wider society.ⁱⁱ Parents and teachers should cooperate because they intent and strain to educate and enable their children, in particular their students, to become diligent, conscientious, capable, and independent in life. Despite their different responsibilities and duties, they should support one another in order to achieve their common educational goals. Feeling confident between parents and teachers, the child is released of the loyalty conflict. As a result of good cooperation, the success of the students will also be good, and thus all three factors will be satisfied. Despite the efforts for change, schools in Kosovo are in a transition period from traditional teaching into reformed teaching. Therefore, the application of some principles of modern teaching philosophy, such as student-centered teaching and parent cooperation also affect positively in the creation of a new spirit for students and the school todayⁱⁱⁱ.

Realizing the importance of school-family cooperation, the school as an organized educational institution must find opportunities and various forms to promote family co-operation. School and family co-operation is realized through different ways and activities of organization with parents in school. Some of these activities will be mentioned below.

The traditional way of cooperation is through individual conversations with parents, general meetings with parents, meetings with the parents' council, etc. Whereas, according to the contemporary way, this is accomplished through: pedagogical workshops, parental schools, school newsletters, thematic panels, family visits, letters sent to parents, questionnaires for parents, seminars, social networks, e-mails, etc.

ⁱⁱ Creating Child-centered Classes (ages 6-7) Step by Step. Institute for Open Society, Tirana, 1999

ⁱⁱⁱ All in School, Prevention and Response to Abandoning and Disrespecting Students at School, Handbook, Pristina, October, 2005, p.9

1.1 Modern Forms

According to pedagogues, modern forms are called forms that have a friendly character of cooperation and create a pleasant atmosphere. These forms of cooperation are organized on different occasions, such as during literary evenings, various school holidays, workshops, picnics, etc.

The most popular forms in the current practice regarding parent-school co-operation are: individual forms, group forms, and collective forms.

1.2 Individual Forms of Co-operation

The individual form of co-operation is one of the ways of direct contact between the teacher and the parents. This form of cooperation deals with the source and true information of students which will help teachers organize their educational activities in general. This form is mostly practiced when the students have a problem, either in family or in school. Therefore, counseling also helps parents' psycho-social and pedagogical education; helping them understanding and identifying violence from similar behaviors, that are not in fact violence^{iv}. Parents with all due respect to teachers, some of them want some things to remain implicit, whether them being related to home, school or of medical character. At the same time, these contacts also benefit the parents who are specifically instructed about the work they have to do with their children at school. This form of co-operation can be realized at the request of the school but also at the initiative of the parents when they feel the need to cooperate with the school. Initiatives from the school can be by the class teacher, psychologist, school educator, etc. Individual meetings can be arranged or come up randomly. Whatever it may be, it is important that the school staff be prepared to accept the parents in these cases and provide them with appropriate advice and suggestions for the purpose of properly informing them about their claims or even problems they might have.

The parent's contact with the teacher and the school is the first condition to realize a mutual trust and cooperation. The contact individually is of special importance because it exceeds the psychological barrier of the official report and the report of both parties having different positions and interests. In this contact, the most important thing is to establish common positions and interests so that later there is no space for conflicts and misunderstandings. However, personal contact between teachers and parents should not avoid the student. This is not a contact where two parties agree on the "account" of a third party. In this communication, the student's active position is also important.

1.3 Group Forms of Communication

This form enables full recognition of the parents; thereby also recognizes parents with educational personnel also with other school parents. This form is usually applied at the beginning of the school year but also at certain periods during the school year. Issues addressed during these contacts are usually for the common interest of all parents.

^{iv} Krasniqi, Islam; Deva Zuna, Afërdita: A School without Violence (How to Do It?) "Libri Shkollor", Pristina 2012, p.289

Within these meetings, smaller groups of parents can be formed who are bound by the shared common interests for their children. All forms of meetings used to enhance the quality of learning are of a co-operative nature and as such, they contribute to the realization and awareness of a fruitful and effective cooperation.

A. Collective actions - they can be used to discuss various problems, namely the parents' concerns for their children. These meetings are important because parents can get important information from the teachers regarding the way in which different problems faced by the school are addressed, as well as sharing their experiences in raising the quality of education.

B. Individual notes – these can be sent to families in order to exchange information about their children. The family can inform the teacher about a particular situation regarding their child, for example, if a child has a particular issue, both health wise or about his/her well-being or skills. In addition, the teacher can inform the family about their child's newly acquired skills and achievements at school, thus his/her overall progress.

C. Meetings with parents - they should be very frequent because they represent a very good form of cooperation, especially when it comes to discussing school plans and programs, possible financial problems, important issues of 'school-to-family' relationship, etc. Parents' meetings as a form of co-operation between school and parents can be organized at school levels, classroom levels, or in the context of a parallel. Parents' meetings are a group form where all parents are called to discuss any need or provide any information that has to do with all students and concerns all the parents. Based on school plans, group meetings for a school year are foreseen to be held for three times a year, but also as needed. At the beginning of the school year, the meeting has to do with information on the requirements of the school, the students, and what should be expected from them throughout the school year. The second meeting is held after the first semester, and the last parental meeting is held at the end of the school year in order to make analysis of the results of student achievements.

Meetings as needed are organized when a request arises, for example organizing any excursion or any special need that the school might have. Also, special meetings can be organized based on the foreseen plan, if needed. These meetings are mostly focused on educational problems. These meetings are usually led by the teacher, but a pedagogue or a school psychologist should also attend the meeting.

D. Meetings within the classroom - These meetings mostly talk about students' success and performance, improving the quality of learning, regular attendance of students at school, excursions and other organization, student's homework, education and development of working habits, cultural and health-hygienic issues, etc.

1.4 School visits

Parents should visit the school in which their children learn. This should be done to recognize their learning environment, to meet the educational staff, other children respectively peers of their children, and in general to become familiar with the school program.

1.5 Phone calls

They can serve specific needs or habits that once a month to be contacted by the family. This is the best way to get details about various elements that are important to student learning aspect and their behaviors.

1.6 Brochures

In many cases the school is preparing leaflets, brochures, posters, etc., and this way affecting the family's awareness of the role and importance of partnership and thus encourage parents for greater co-operation.

1.7 Newspapers for parents

This contemporary form of recent decades is also being implemented in our schools. These papers are devoted to parents and rely on written words, drawings and photographs. The newspaper should have adequate terminology that will be close to the parent's educational structure, with specific and concrete goals. The newspaper is prepared by the teachers together with the students; they define topics related to the acceptance of novelties and the discarding of some stereotypes and prejudices that their parents might have. The school newspaper is one of the most effective ways to communicate with parents, students, and the community in general. The more the newspaper is sent to the parents, the more powerful the relationship between the family and the school will be, and parents will feel more secure in this partnership.

1.8 Visits to students' families

These visits can be done from the child's integration to the school. This will be very useful when we want to understand the family circumstances in which the child lives and grows. The school subject through these visits is directly acquainted with working conditions, with other close or wider family members, and with other specifics related to the child's life.

According to pedagogues, this form should be planned. Visiting student's families are very important because it best studies all the problems that are controversial or preoccupying the students. At the same time these activity is also a high pedagogical pre-qualification. Visits have certain goals; to be informed about children's progress, behavior, discipline, and many other educational problems. Family visits that teachers conduct can highly strengthen the school-family relationship. In addition, a group role, weekly messages, suggestion boxes, social networking, etc. can also play an important role in strengthening the family-school relationship.

2. Conclusion

Parents, teachers, and schools have the primary purpose of developing and advancing the children. The need for parent and teacher co-operation is a key link for the realization of educational tasks and purposes. With the cooperation of these two factors, the school can better acquaint the students with the skills, habits and status of the

families. However, given that, each school has its own specific features; it is therefore a primary task for each school to build its own work on studying the situation of students and parents at the general level of concern for children, teachers, and parents.

In the family-school or parent-teacher co-operation, in the reformed school system, in continuity, stronger cooperation is required. However, much work still needs to be done in this regard because all parents want their children to progress in the lessons and in all the activities organized by the school. Today, the level of parents' awareness is greater; they now feel more responsible for educating their children.

Given how the cooperation between parents and teachers has worked in the past, we can say that. Today positive transformations have been made in this regard. It is an archaic idea that when a child goes to school, the parent's concern for education is left to the school and the teachers alone. Nevertheless, it should not be forgotten that the problem of education belongs to the whole society, not just teachers and parents. This cooperation even earlier in the history of education development has been one of the basic conditions for understanding the child and his progress.

Parent-teacher relations also depend on the position of the society where the school and family are located and the impacts of the social context of their development. Many pedagogues, psychologists, sociologists who have taken interdisciplinary studies, especially with the problem of family-school cooperation, have sought to find the means by which the goal will be achieved.

Bibliography

1. Nushi, Pajazit, Dictionary of Psychology, Prishtina, 1987
2. Kozma, Grillo, Dictionary of Education, Tirana, 2002 pg.74
3. Hyseni, Halim; Nikoleta, Mita; Salihaj, Jonuz; Pupovci, Dukagjin, Governance and Education Leadership, KEC, Pristina, 2003
4. Kraja, Musa; Pedagogy, Tirana, 1988
5. Creating Child-centered Classes (ages 6-7) Step by Step. Institute for Open Society, Tirana, 1999
6. Dërvodeli, Januz, Information and professional orientation, Etruria, Pristina, 1997
7. Fullan, Majkell, The Force of Change, Tirana, 2002.
8. Krasniqi, Islam; Deva Zuna, Afërdita., A School Without Violence (How to Do It), "Libri Shkollor" Pristina 2012

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